

ANN HYBRID MODEL FOR DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF CONVENTIONAL MPA

Prakash Chandra Mishra¹, Rakesh Kumar Maurya², Ravi Prakash Prajapati³

^{1,2} Department of Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering, Faculty of Engineering and technology, MJP, Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, (U.P) INDIA

³ Department of Electronics Engineering, Institute of Engineering and Technology, VBS, Purvanchal University, Jaunpur, U.P-222001,INDIA.

ABSTRACT: A hybrid model based on ANN is offered to calculate simultaneously the resonant frequencies of various microstrips patch antennas (MPAs) of traditional geometry. The ANN hybrid model is trained with the back propagation algorithm to calculate the resonant frequencies of MPAs. The resonant frequency results of proposed ANN hybrid method for the rectangular, circular, and triangular MPAs are in very good agreement with the experimental results available in the literatures. The results are also validated by fabricating randomly picked one data set of circular MPAs. Antenna designers can use the proposed models quickly and simply in analysis and synthesis of conventional antenna without the need for complex processes for CAD and other microwave applications.

KEYWORDS: Hybrid Model, Conventional MPA, Resonant Frequency, Artificial Neural Network.

I. INTRODUCTION

Microstrip patch antennas (MPAs) are used in a broad range of applications from communication systems to biomedical systems, first and foremost due to their simplicity, conformability, low mechanized cost, light weight, low profile, reproducibility, reliability, and ease in fabrication and integration with solid-state devices [1-4]. These gorgeous features have recently increased the application of MPAs and stimulated greater effort to investigate their performance. The patch of traditional microstrip antenna may be of any shape. The most commonly used traditional MPAs are circular, rectangular, and triangular. These patches are used due to their simplicity and the most demanding in several applications [5-6]. In MPAs designs, because they operate only in the environs of resonance frequency hence, it needs to be calculated precisely for analyzing the microstrip antennas. Similarly, for designing the MPAs, the physical dimensions of patches must also be calculated accurately. Several traditional methods have been used for computing the resonance frequency of circular MPAs [7-9]. These methods are considered as analytical methods and numerical methods.

The analytical methods provide impulsive explanation for the operation of MPAs and based on the physical assumptions. The numerical methods provide precise results but only at the cost of rigorous mathematical calculation and time consumption [10-12]. In present scenario, most powerful commercially available simulation software's such as IE3D, HFSS and CST studio etc are widely used for analysis of any conventional or complex MPAs [13-17]. These simulation software works on trial and error basis and again more time consuming methods with low probability to achieve desired goals. The other problems on these methods are, it require a new solution even for a minor change in the patch geometry. Thus, if we require a new solution with minor alteration in the patch geometry and as well as change in the substrates material, these methods leads to complexities and more time consumption.

In recent years the ANN, ANFIS, SVM etc models are preferred for analyzing and synthesizing the MPAs [18-23] due to their ability and adaptability to learning, generalization, smaller information requirement, fast real-time operation, and ease of implementation features These models are trained by using measured, calculated, and/or simulated patterns of data sets. The aim of the training process is to minimize error between reference and actual outputs of the models. Once the model is trained for a precise error, it returns the results very fast.

In this proposed work, authors have projected a simple and accurate calculation of resonant frequency of circular, rectangular, and triangular MPAs in a single ANN model. Author also fabricated one of circular MPA and measured the result for further validation of results of ANN model. The proposed analysis approach is based on making equal dimensions in the input patterns of these three MPAs before training. The data sets for training and testing of hybrid models in this paper have been taken from previous experimental works, which is instantly collected from Kerim Guney et.al [24].

II. HYBRID STRUCTURES AND DATA COLLECTION

After survey of many literatures it is evidently found that the resonant frequencies of the traditional (circular, rectangular, and triangular) MPAs are depend on patch dimensions (radius a of circular, length l and width w of rectangular and side s of triangular), substrate material (height h and relative permittivity ϵ_r) and modes (m and n). To calculate the resonant frequencies of these traditional MPAs by using the hybrid method, their dimensions should be equated. In Fig. 1 shows equated area of MPAs and equation (1) and (2) shows their formulas to equivalent dimensions of the circular and triangular patches with reference to rectangular patch.

Fig.1 Equivalent Diagram for hybridization of circular, rectangular and Triangular MPAs

$$w = \frac{\pi \cdot a}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad l = 2 \cdot a \quad \text{for circular MPA..... (1)}$$

$$w = \frac{s}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad l = d \quad \text{for triangular MPA..... (2)}$$

where d is the height of triangular patch. It can be seen that from equation of (1) and (2) by multiplying w by l is equal to area of the scrupulous patch. Hence the calculation of resonant frequency by ANN hybrid method, the parameter w, l, h, ϵ_r, m and n are considered inputs for all MPAs, where m and n are their fundamental modes.

A good collection of the training data that are well distributed and accurately simulated is the basic requirement to obtain an accurate model. The data can be collected by measurement and simulation. The assortment of a data generator depends on the application and availability of the data generator. The training and test datasets used in this paper have been obtained from previous experimental works. A total of 68 data sets are listed in tables 1 for circular, rectangular and triangular MPA. Apart from 68 data set 56 data sets were used to train the model, and the remaining 12 data sets, marked with ('*') in tables 1, were used for testing. The equivalent values of w and l for the circular and triangular MPAs were calculated by using equation (1) and (2). In order to facilitate an effective learning process, the elements of each row of the input-output data sets were scaled with respect to the row minimum and maximum values including relative permittivity for transforming their range between zero and one before training. The data sets for training and testing ("*" marks) for ANN hybrid models of circular, rectangular and triangular are collected from literature and shown in table 1 (a), (b) and (c) respectively.

Table-1 Resonant Frequency of (a) Circular MPAs (for $m=1, n=1$), (b) Rectangular MPAs ($m=1, n=0$) (c) Triangular MPAs for different modes [24].

(a)				
Sl. No. of Patch	a (cm)	h (cm)	ϵ_r	f_{ME} (MHz)
1	6.8	0.08	2.32	835
2	6.8	0.159	2.32	829
3	6.8	0.318	2.32	815
*4	5.0	0.159	2.32	1128
5	3.8	0.1524	2.49	1443

6	4.85	0.318	2.52	1099
7	3.493	0.1588	2.50	1570
#*8	1.27	0.0794	2.59	4070
9	3.493	0.3175	2.50	1510
10	4.95	0.235	4.55	825
11	3.975	0.235	4.55	1030
12	2.99	0.235	4.55	1360
*13	2.0	0.235	4.55	2003
14	1.04	0.235	4.55	3750
15	0.77	0.235	4.55	4945
16	1.15	0.15875	2.65	4425
*17	1.07	0.15875	2.65	4723
18	0.96	0.15875	2.65	5224
19	0.74	0.15875	2.65	6634
20	0.82	0.15875	2.65	6074

(b)

Sl. No. of Patch	w (cm)	l (cm)	h (cm)	ϵ_r	f_{ME} (MHz)
21	0.85	1.290	0.017	2.22	7740
22	0.79	1.185	0.017	2.22	8450
*23	2.0	2.5	0.79	2.22	3970
24	1.063	1.183	0.79	2.55	7730
25	0.91	1.0	0.127	10.2	4600
26	1.72	1.86	0.157	2.33	5060
27	1.81	1.96	0.157	2.33	4805
*28	1.27	1.35	0.163	2.55	6560
29	1.5	1.621	0.163	2.55	5600
30	1.337	1.412	0.2	2.55	6200
31	1.12	1.2	0.242	2.55	7050
32	1.403	1.485	0.252	2.55	5800
33	1.53	1.63	0.3	2.5	5270
*34	0.905	1.018	0.3	2.5	7990
35	1.17	1.28	0.3	2.5	6570
36	1.375	1.58	0.476	2.55	5100
37	0.776	1.08	0.33	2.55	8000
38	0.79	1.255	0.4	2.55	7134
39	0.987	1.45	0.45	2.55	6070

40	1.0	1.52	0.476	2.55	5820
*41	0.814	1.44	0.476	2.55	6380
42	0.79	1.62	0.550	2.55	5990
43	1.2	1.97	0.626	2.55	4660
44	0.783	2.3	0.854	2.55	4600
45	1.256	2.756	0.952	2.55	3580
46	0.974	2.62	0.952	2.55	3980
47	1.02	2.64	0.952	2.55	3900
48	0.883	2.676	1.0	2.55	3980
*49	0.777	2.835	1.1	2.55	3900
50	0.92	3.130	1.2	2.55	3470
51	1.03	3.38	1.281	2.55	3200
52	1.265	3.5	1.281	2.55	2980
53	1.08	3.4	1.281	2.55	3150

(c)					
Sl. No. of Patch	Mode	s (cm)	h (cm)	ϵ_r	f_{ME} (MHz)
54	TM ₁₀	4.1	0.07	10.5	1519
55	TM ₁₁	4.1	0.07	10.5	2637
56	TM ₂₀	4.1	0.07	10.5	2995
*57	TM ₂₁	4.1	0.07	10.5	3973
58	TM ₃₀	4.1	0.07	10.5	4439
59	TM ₁₀	8.7	0.078	2.32	1489
60	TM ₁₁	8.7	0.078	2.32	2596
*61	TM ₂₀	8.7	0.078	2.32	2969
62	TM ₂₁	8.7	0.078	2.32	3968
63	TM ₃₀	8.7	0.078	2.32	4443
64	TM ₁₀	10	0.159	2.32	1280
65	TM ₁₁	10	0.159	2.32	2242
*66	TM ₂₀	10	0.159	2.32	2550
67	TM ₂₁	10	0.159	2.32	3400
68	TM ₃₀	10	0.159	2.32	3824
“*” Test data sets			# fabricated data set		

III. DESIGN OF ANN HYBRID MODELS AND TESTING

The basic block diagram to design ANN/ANFIS hybrid model is shown in fig.2. The training and testing of models performed in the given fashion. In the training process inputs ($w, l, a, h, \epsilon_r, m, n$) and target (f_{me}) from data sets of table 1, both are used as input data. In the internal process target value (f_{me}) is compared by result of training (f_{ANN}/f_{ANFIS}) in each iteration and training error is checked by mean square error (MSE) performance graph. Error

derivatives are then calculated and summed up for each weight until all the training sets have been accessible to the network. These error derivatives are then used to renovate the weights for neurons in the model. In the process of training, when MSE is found near to threshold value, then training has been stopped and the model is ready. The trained ANN/ANFIS model basically establishes the relationship between the parameters of the microstrip antennas (MSAs) and the measured resonant frequency results. After completing the training process, the ANN/ANFIS hybrid model is ready for testing. The test data sets are also shown in table 1 with “*” mark. In the test data sets only the input parameter is used in trained hybrid model and find out the output f_{ANN} / f_{ANFIS} . These test results are shown in table 3 and compared by measured results.

Fig. 2 Basic block diagram for design of ANN hybrid models

3.1 ANN HYBRID MODEL

ANN is one of the most intelligent, fast and flexible tool to model nonlinear relation, simulation, and optimization of antenna. In the itinerary of beginning an ANN model, the architecture of the neural network and their learning algorithm are two most important factors. ANNs have many architecture and algorithm, and selection depends on the dilemma to be solved. After a number of trials using different architectures attached with different training algorithms, the multilayered perceptron (MLP) neural network architecture and back propagation algorithm found suitable to compute the resonant frequencies of MPAs. The MLPs have a many layer structure and neurons in each layer are entirely interconnected, with weights controlling the strength of the links. After many trials, by changing the epoch, neurons and activation functions in layers, high accuracy is achieved using MLP with two hidden layered network. Finally, the model has total 4 layers (two hidden layers, one input layer and one output layer). The best suitable network configurations for ANN hybrid model, which are found, are given in table-2 and model shown in fig. 3.

Table-2 Basic Parameters Value Used In Ann Model

Parameters	Value
Inputs	6
Targets/ outputs	3
Network type	MLP (Multi layer Perceptron)
Algorithms	Back Propagation
Layers	4 (1 input, 2 hidden , 1output)
Network configuration	6×24×16×1
Input and Output activation function	Linear
Hidden layer activation function	Tansigmoidal
Traing epoch	648
Momentum coefficient	0.01
Learning rate	0.9

Fig.3 ANN Hybrid model for resonant frequency calculation of circular, rectangular, and triangular MPAs.

IV. FABRICATION & MEASUREMENT OF CIRCULAR MPA

In order to further validation of ANN hybrid model, a randomly selected circular patch antenna is fabricated and measured on Agilent vector network analyzer. For fabrication the antenna is randomly selected from test data set of circular MPA shown in table 1 with “#” mark. The geometry of is shown in fig. 4. The measured result of resonant frequency for fabricated antenna ($F_{fabricated}$) is shown in table 3. The measured result shows very good agreement with results of ANN hybrid models.

Fig.4 Geometry of fabricated circular MPA (a) Top view (b) Side view (c) Photograph

Table-3 Resonant Frequency results of ANN hybrid model for test data sets (“*” mark in table 1) and measured result of fabricated circular MPA (“#”) and their APE

Patch Sl. No.	f_{ME} (MHz)	f_{ANN} (MHz)	$F_{fabricated}$ (MHz)
4	1128	1127.8	
#8	4070	4068.5	4069.41
13	2003	2002.7	
17	4723	4723.8	
23	3970	3970.2	
28	6560	6561.2	
34	7990	7990.6	
41	6380	6380.7	
49	3900	3899.5	

57	3973	7974.1	
61	2969	2969.8	
66	2550	2550.5	
Average Percentage Error (APE)		0.0713	

“#” data set used for fabrication

V. RESULT, CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE

The resonant frequencies of conventional MPA calculated by proposed ANN hybrid model for test data sets of the rectangular, circular, and triangular MPAs are listed in table 3. The results obtained by using the ANN hybrid model are in very good agreement with measured results (collected by literature). The sum of the absolute percentage errors (APE) between the hybrid models and measured results are also listed in table 3. The APE is calculated by:

$$APE = \frac{\sum |(f_{ME} - f_{ANN / ANFIS}) / f_{ME}|}{number\ of\ antenna} \times 100 \tag{3}$$

It can be seen from table 3; the very low APE values support the validity of the hybrid methods. For further validation of result one randomly selected circular MPA is fabricated and measured. This measured result also shows very good agreement with results of hybrid models. It needs to be emphasized here, that the better results may be obtained by choosing other training and test data sets from the ones used in this paper, or by collecting more data sets values for training.

Hence the proposed hybrid method is convincing for the resonant frequency computation of all three different types of conventional MPAs, like rectangular, circular, and triangular. The hybrid method is presented to accurately and simultaneously compute the resonant frequencies of all the three conventional MPAs. The main benefit of the hybrid method proposed here is that the model can be used to simultaneously calculate the resonant frequencies of proposed MPAs. The proposed hybrid method is not limited to the resonant frequency computation of MPAs even it can be also used to other antenna and microwave related problems. The quick featured of the hybrid method recommends in the application of antenna computer-aided design (CAD) programs and as well as in application of microwave and electromagnetic engineering.

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